

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

NTN1 (netrin 1)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID	9423 / O95631
Target Nominator	AMP-AD, TREAT-AD
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SUMMARY OF PROJECT

NTN1 is an axon outgrowth guidance cue that works in association with APP in development and adulthood [1,2]. Our work identified NTN1 as a core element of a proteomic module associated with AD pathology and cognitive decline. This project is focused upon the development of a target enabling package (TEP) of resources to help the scientific community advance its future study of NTN1 in AD associated processes. Those resources include a validated antibody that functions to specifically identify NTN1 in immortalized cell lines; purified protein for biochemical investigations and a full bioinformatic workup of the NTN1 gene. We aim for these resources to promote the further investigation of NTN1.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Netrin-1 (NTN1) is a protein that belongs to the netrin family, which is part of a larger group of proteins involved in axonal guidance and cell migration [3,4]. Structurally, Netrin-1 has several distinct domains: 1) the N-terminal signal sequence targeting the protein into the secretory pathway, 2) the N-terminal laminin domains homologous with core elements of the extracellular matrix protein laminin, and 3) three EGF-like repeats which are involved in ligand binding and extracellular protein interactions, 4) C-terminal region homologue with the N-terminal regions of netrin G1 and G2 [3,4]. The combination of these domains allows Netrin-1 to interact with various receptors and components of the extracellular matrix, facilitating its role in guiding cellular and axonal migration. Netrin-1 plays crucial roles in both the development of the nervous system and in adult physiology. During neural development, Netrin-1 serves as a guidance cue for axons, directing them to their correct targets. It can act as both an attractant and a repellent depending on the receptor it binds to [1]. Beyond its role in the nervous system, Netrin-1 is involved in the development and maintenance of several other tissues. For example, it plays a role in lung branching morphogenesis [5] and in the modulation of inflammatory responses [6].

The association of NTN1 with neurodegeneration, and specifically Alzheimer's disease (AD), has been a subject of growing interest. Research has indicated several potential roles of NTN1 in the pathophysiology of AD. NTN1 is crucial for neuronal survival and axonal guidance, as mentioned above, and its signaling pathways can prevent neuronal apoptosis, particularly in dopaminergic neurons in Parkinson's disease [7]. In other cortical neurons, NTN1 may impact neuronal survival through the modulation of APP proteolysis - as NTN1 complexes with APP and Studies suggest that Netrin-1 can influence the processing of amyloid precursor protein (APP), a critical protein involved in AD. Specifically, Netrin-1 has been shown to inhibit the production of amyloid-beta (A β) peptides, which aggregate to form plaques in the brains of AD patients. This inhibition occurs through the direct interaction with APP, and subsequently modifies its proteolytic processing [2]; interestingly, APP may reciprocally regulate the activity of NTN1 axon outgrowth [8]. The bidirectional regulation of NTN1 and APP may imply a strong functional interaction, consistent with both being involved in axon outgrowth in neurodevelopment. NTN1 may also reduce the toxicity of A β peptides.

Concordantly, NTN1 also decreases the amyloid induced synaptic impairment, suggesting a role in synaptic integrity in the presence of AD pathology [9,10]. In our work, NTN1 was identified as a core protein within a proteomic module tightly associated with cognitive decline and AD pathological advancement [11]. Considerable work remains to identify the role of NTN1 in AD pathology, or the likely neuroprotective effect it exerts in the presence of degenerative cascades, and we hope the resources that TREAT-AD has developed will facilitate these efforts.

BIOINFORMATIC ANALYSIS

Target Source & Hypothesis

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#) [12]. This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for NTN1 is 3.68 out of 5 (rank #1180, 95th percentile) (**Fig. 1A**). The individual score components include 1.7 of 3 for genetics (72nd percentile) (**Fig. 1B**), and 1.99 out of 2 for genomics (97th percentile) (**Fig. 1C**). The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of NTN1, both protein and RNA, is significantly higher in brains from patients with AD (**Fig. 1C**).

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD) (sea-ad.org, [13]). Gene expression was averaged across cells within a supertype from each donor. The locally weighted mean expression (LOWESS) of superotypes within each subclass is then plotted across the range of continuous donor pseudo-progression, which orders subjects based on a learned model of neuropathological burden. NTN1 is expressed primarily in OPC cell types from the SEA-AD dataset. NTN1 expression is stable within cell types subclasses across donor pseudo-progression (**Fig. 1D**).

Figure 1. (A) TREAT-AD Target Risk Score, and component (B) genetic risk score and (C) multi-omic risk score. The lines within the score and component score violin plots show the 50th and 90th percentile scores. (D) NTN1 cell type expression data from SEA-AD. Cell type expression plots show the locally weighted mean expression of cell superotypes from each donor within each subclass along donor pseudo-progression.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (“biodomains”) [12]. These biodomains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biodomains via GO term annotations. NTN1 is annotated to GO terms from 3 biodomains, primarily to terms from the Synapse, Structural Stabilization, and Apoptosis domains (**Fig. 2A**).

The CRISPRbrain resource (crisprbrain.org, [14]) is a data commons for functional genomics datasets from differentiated human iPSC derived cell types. The resource reports phenotype results following CRISPR screens of gene activation (CRISPRa), inhibition (CRISPRi), or gene knockout (CRISPRn), in iPSC derived brain-relevant cell types. Following the screens, genes are identified as either positive or negative hits, meaning perturbation leads to a significant and reproducible increase or decrease in the measured phenotype, respectively, or a non-hit if the perturbation does not significantly impact the phenotype. NTN1 is not a hit in any assay (**Fig. 2B**).

Figure 2. (A) NTN1 TREAT-AD biological domain annotations and **(B)** phenotypes from CRISPR screens in iPSC derived cell types from the CRISPRbrain resource.

VALIDATED ANTIBODIES AND KNOCKOUT CELL LINES

YCharOS Antibody Characterization

The Antibody Characterization through Open Science (YCharOS) initiative, led from McGill University, is a global, public-good effort uniting academic researchers, funding agencies, 13 leading antibody manufacturers, and two knockout cell line providers. Using industry-endorsed protocols [15], YCharOS systematically evaluates antibody performance with the goal of identifying one or more high-quality renewable antibodies

(e.g., monoclonal or recombinant) per human protein target. Antibodies are tested side-by-side in immunoblot (western blot), immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using isogenic knockout cell lines as controls. All results are shared openly and rapidly via the AD Knowledge Portal (<https://adknowledgeportal.synapse.org/>) and in the Zenodo YCharOS community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/treatad/>).

YCharOS has identified the MCF7 cell line background with adequate NTN1 protein expression, and an MCF7 *NTN1* knockout line was obtained from Abcam and used to characterize NTN1 antibodies. YCharOS' partners contributed 14 NTN1 antibodies which were tested side-by-side by immunoblot and immunoprecipitation. Renewable antibodies were found to be specific for both applications. Intracellular NTN1 was detected at much lower levels than the secreted protein and the immunofluorescence assay was thus dismissed in this report. The antibody characterization report generated by YCharOS is available on Zenodo. Complete report: [NTN1 antibody characterization report](#) [16].

PROTEIN CONSTRUCTS AND EXPRESSION METHODS

Protein Purified

1. NTN1 39-453 AviN HisC (PBC040-C02): Baculovirus expression for structure determination; may not be full ORF

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

CONCLUSION

NTN1, a gene related to axon guidance with some notable intersections with APP processing and regulation, was selected by TREAT-AD as a potential AD target based on an extensive bioinformatic analysis including an integrative target ranking score. Here, we present the results of this bioinformatic evaluation, including genetic and genomic risk as well as brain cell subtype expression. We report increased levels of NTN1 at both the RNA and protein levels in brains from AD patients.

In order to promote the continued investigation of the potential roles of NTN1 in AD pathophysiology, we next performed a standardized evaluation of commercially available antibodies specific for NTN1 protein using knock-out cell lines, and identified several renewable antibodies which were suitable for immunoblot and immunoprecipitation assays. Of note, the presence of NTN1 was found to be highest in media (secreted) rather than in lysates (intracellular). To date, we have also generated one baculovirus expression construct for NTN1 protein purification for potential use in structure determination amongst other applications. Overall, the tools presented here provide a foundation for further determination of the role of NTN1 in AD by interested investigators in the scientific community.

FUNDING INFORMATION

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ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Method

1. Protein Expression and Purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

Gene name	NTN1
Uniprot ID	O95631
Region	39-453

Description	Laminin-like protein that plays a role in regulating macrophage persistence and chronic inflammation in atherosclerosis and obesity.
Synonyms	NTN1L
Construct ID	NTN1_39-453_AviN_HisC (PBC040-C02)
Parental Vector	pFHMSP-AviN-LIC-C
Tag (N-terminal)	MKFLVNVALVFMVVYISYIYAAAGSAGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSG
Tag (C-terminal)	EFVEHHHHHHHH
Protein mass (with tag)	53462.20 Da
Extinction Coefficient with tag ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	56445
Protein sequence (with tag)	MKFLVNVALVFMVVYISYIYAAAGSAGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSGDPCSDENG HPRRCIPDFVNAAFVKDVRVSSTCGRPPARYCVVSEGEERLRSCHLCNASDPKKA HPPAFLTDLNNPHNLTCWQSENYLQFPHNVTLTLSLGGKFEVTVSLQFCSPRPES MAIYKSM DYGR TWVPFQFYSTQCRKMYNRPHRAPITKQNEQEAVCTDSHTDMRP LSGGLIAFSTLDGRPSAHD FDN SPVLQDWVTATDIRVAFSRLHTFGDENEDDSELAR DSYFYAVSDLQVGGRCCKNGHAARCVRDRDDSLVCD CRHNTAGPECDRCKPFHY DRPWQRATAREANECVACN CNLHARRCRFMELYKLSGRKSGGVCLNCRHNTAG RHCHYCKEGYYRDMGKPITHRKACKACDHPVGAAGKTCNQTTGQCPCCKDGV TG ITCNRCAKGYQQSRSPIAPCIKEFVEHHHHHHHH

Purified Protein	
SEC (step 2): NTN1_39-453_AviN_HisC	
Intact Mass Deconvolution:	N/A
Observed Mass:	N/A
Protein yield:	0.3 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	Insect cells: Sf9 (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>)
Expression Medium	I-Max Insect Media W/ L-Glutamine, Wisent Biocentre
Transformation and storage	The baculovirus expression vector system (BEVS), specifically Bac-to-Bac Expression System (Invitrogen), employing <i>Autographa californica</i> multiple nucleopolyhedrovirus (AcMNPV) has been used for expression screening and production of target protein. The plasmid transfer vector containing the gene of interest was transformed into DH10Bac <i>E. coli</i> competent cells to generate recombinant viral bacmid DNA. Adherent Sf9 cells were then transfected with bacmid DNA to generate recombinant viruses used for the baculovirus-mediated production in the insect cells.
Expression	For the scale-up productions, suspension cultures of the baculovirus-infected insect cells, (SCBIIC) were prepared by infection of the Sf9 cells with the corresponding P2 viruses. On the day of production, 2 L of Sf9 cells (cell viability > 97%) in 2.5 L Tunair shake flasks or 4 L in 5 L reagent bottles were diluted to a cell density of 4×10^6 /mL. These cells were infected directly with 10-12 mL/L of suspension culture of baculovirus-infected insect cells and incubated at a lowered temperature of 25 °C, at 145 rpm. Infected cells' density and viability along with the cell sizes monitored after 72 hours post-infection time to be able to collect cells for purification at the optimal conditions when Sf9 cells are well infected, usually in 5-6 days after the post-infection time.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. Wash Buffer: 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 5 mM imidazole 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 250 mM imidazole 4. SEC buffer: 20 mM HEPES (pH 7.4), 300 mM NaCl, 2mM TCEP 5. TALON beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spin down cells @6500RPM for 15min

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Transfer each 1.5L supernatant to a 2.8L flask with 150ml 10X PBS. 3. Add (2ml/L) Ni-sepharose beads to the supernatant and shake at 100RPM at 18 °C for 60 min. 4. Transfer the supernatant + beads to an open column to collect the beads and keep the flowthrough. 5. Wash beads with 50CV of lysis buffer. 6. Wash column with 1CV of wash buffer. 7. Elute protein with 5CV elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. 8. Add beads (2ml /L) to the collected flowthrough for second binding same condition and repeat the same wash and elution after 1hour shaking.
Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 26/60 column in SEC buffer at 3 ml/min. 2. Analyze fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 1.3 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 3. Snap-freeze aliquots in PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

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